

A Hospital-Based Assessment of the Acquired Demyelinating Diseases in Children: A Retrospective Study

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to assess the acquired demyelinating diseases in children.

Methods: The present study was conducted in the Department of Paediatrics, IGIMS, Patna, Bihar, India from December 2016 to November 2018. A total of 50 patients were enrolled in the study.

Results: Of these, 33 (66%) cases were of acquired demyelinating encephalomyelitis (ADEM), 10 (20%) of transverse myelitis (TM), 5 (10%) of neuromyelitis optica (NMO), 1 (2%) of optic neuritis (ON) and 1 (2%) of multiple sclerosis (MS). The mean age of presentation was 7.7 years (range: 2-12 years). Of 50 cases, 24 (48%) were male and 26 (52%) females. History of preceding illness was present as upper respiratory infection /acute febrile illness and mean duration between preceding events and onset of symptoms was 7.24±2.9 days. All patients diagnosed with ADEM had encephalopathy. Areas involved in descending order of frequency were subcortical white matter, basal ganglia, thalamus, brainstem, cerebellum and spinal cord involvement.

Conclusion: Children presenting with new, subacute focal neurological deficits with history of some preceding event and in absence of trauma, metabolic derangements, or structural abnormalities should be suspected of having acquired CNS demyelination. These patients should be investigated with CSF analysis, serum antibodies and neuroimaging. ADEM is the most common among ADS. Early diagnosis and management with steroid therapy improves outcome in most of the patients.

Keywords: Pediatric demyelinating disorders, ADEM, Transverse myelitis, MOG

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Introduction

Acquired demyelinating syndromes (ADS) can be defined as syndromes resulting in single (monofocal) or multiple (polyfocal) lesions originating in the central nervous system (CNS) caused by inflammatory demyelination. Monophasic events may be classified as (1) clinically isolated syndrome (CIS), characterized by monofocal or polyfocal deficits without encephalopathy, or (2) acute disseminated encephalomyelitis (ADEM), characterized by polyfocal deficits and encephalopathy. Recurrent disorders include pediatric multiple sclerosis (MS), neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorders (NMOSD), and serum antibodies to myelin oligodendrocyte glycoprotein (MOG)-associated demyelination. [1]

Optic neuritis (ON) is characterized by inflammation of the optic nerve. It may present as an isolated condition or can be associated with variety of other immune-mediated CNS or systemic disorders. [2] Mean age of onset ranges from 9 to 12 years of age with an approximate 1.5:1 female-to-male ratio. [3] Its incidence is 1–5 per 100,000/year.

[3] Between 13% and 36% of children with an initial episode of ON are eventually diagnosed with MS. [4]

Clinical Features Common clinical features of ON include periorbital pain or headache made worse by eye movement, subacute decrease in visual acuity (VA), abnormal color vision, reduced low-contrast letter acuity, and visual field (VF) defects. Physical examination at the time of an acute event will reveal a relative afferent pupillary defect (RAPD) in unilateral cases. Initial visual acuity can range from 20/40 or better to no light perception. Close to 60% of children have a VA of 20/200 or worse. [5] Inflammation of the optic nerve head (papillitis) is reported in up to 64% of cases of ON in children. [6] Bilateral ON and papillitis at onset are seen in 72% of children younger than 10 years of age, in comparison to older children. [5] The absence of pain and presence of retinal exudates, retinal hemorrhages, severe disk swelling, and lack of response to treatment suggest alternative diagnosis

MRI of the CNS is critical in the accurate diagnosis and classification of an acquired demyelinating syndrome. MRI should be obtained with gadolinium contrast and should include the area of the CNS that is impacted (eg, MRI of the brain and orbits for an optic neuritis, MRI of the spinal cord for those with a myelitis presentation). Imaging outside the area affected can also yield important prognostic information. In children presenting with acute transverse myelitis, lesions within the brain bode a significant future risk for relapse and ultimate MS diagnosis. [7]

The aim of the present study was to assess the acquired demyelinating diseases in children.

Materials and Methods

The present study was conducted in the Department of Pediatrics, IGIMS, Patna, Bihar, India from December 2016 to November 2018. A total of 50 patients were enrolled in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

All children in the age group between 1 year to 12 years who present with clinical, radiological, and immunological features of acquired demyelinating disorders were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

Parents/ guardians not willing to give written informed consent to enroll their child in the study were excluded from the study.

The study was performed in accordance with the ethical principles specified in the declaration of Helsinki and as per the guidelines of good clinical practice.

Statistical Analysis

After data collection, data entry was done in a Microsoft Excel sheet. Data analysis was done with the help of statistical software GraphPad InStat.v3.0. Data were presented in tables as well as figures, wherever needed descriptive statistics were used to note down the distribution of patients based on age, gender, patient history details, and other findings. A p value of less than 0.05 was considered significant wherever applicable.

Brief Methodology Details

After enrollment, demographic details such as age, sex and socioeconomic status were noted in the predesigned proforma. Patient details were noted as follows-Detailed patient history, complete physical and neurological examination and laboratory investigations-Routine blood (CBC, liver and renal function test), serum antibodies for MOG and AQP-4, CSF analysis and MRI (brain/spine) scan.

The diagnosis of ADS was based on the acute onset of neurologic signs and symptoms together with brain MRI evidence of multifocal, hyperintense lesions on T2- weighted according to IPMSSG 2010 criterion.

Results

Table 1: Frequency distribution of age groups with acquired demyelinating diseases

Age groups(Years)	ADEM	TM	NMO	MS	ON	Total (%)
1 to 4	7	2	0	0	0	9 (18)
5 to 8	14	2	1	0	0	17 (34)
9 to 12	12	6	4	1	1	24 (48)
Total	33	10	5	1	1	50 (100)
Mean ± SD	7.04±3.09	8.5±3.34	9.16±2.3	12	12	7.7±3.07

Of these, 33 (66%) cases were of acquired demyelinating encephalomyelitis (ADEM), 10 (20%) of transverse myelitis (TM), 5 (10%) of neuromyelitis optica (NMO), 1 (2%) of optic neuritis (ON) and 1 (2%) of multiple sclerosis (MS). The mean age of presentation was 7.7 years (range: 2-12 years).

Table 2: Frequency distribution of gender of patients with acquired demyelinating diseases

Gender	ADEM	TM	NMO	MS	ON	Total (%)
Male	21	2	0	0	1	24 (48)
Female	12	8	5	1	0	26 (52)
Total	33	10	5	1	1	50 (100)

Of 50 cases, 24 (48%) were male and 26 (52%) females.

Table 3: Clinical features of pediatric demyelinating disorders

Clinical features	ADEM, (n=33)	TM, (n=10)	NMO, (n=5)	ON, (n=1)	MS, (n=1)
Encephalopathy	33	-	1	-	-
Seizures	8	-	-	-	-
Fever	6	-	-	-	-
Visual disturbances	-	-	5	1	-
Unilateral	-	-	-	1	-
Bilateral	-	-	5	-	-
Limb weakness	17	10	5	-	1
Hemiparesis	5	-	-	-	-
Paraparesis	2	8	5	-	-
Quadriparesis	10	3	-	-	1
Cerebellar signs	9	-	-	-	-
Sensory involvement	-	10	2	-	-
Meningism	18	-	-	-	-
Bowel and bladder involvement	4	10	2	-	-
Recurrent history	4	-	-	-	1

History of preceding illness was present as upper respiratory infection /acute febrile illness and mean duration between preceding events and onset of symptoms was 7.24±2.9 days. All patients diagnosed with ADEM had encephalopathy.

Table 4: Radiological findings of pediatric demyelinating disorders

Radiological findings	ADEM, (n=33)	LETM, (n=10)	NMO, (n=5)	ON, (n=1)	MS, (n=1)
Areas involved					
Cerebral cortex	30	-	1	-	1
Thalamus	18	-	1	-	-
Brainstem	14	-	2	-	-
Cerebellum	10	-	1	-	1
Spine	2	10	5	-	-
Optic nerve	-	-	5	1	-
Contrast enhancement	7	-	1	-	1

Areas involved in descending order of frequency were subcortical white matter, basal ganglia, thalamus, brainstem, cerebellum and spinal cord involvement.

Discussion

Acquired demyelinating diseases (ADS) constitute a heterogeneous group of central nervous system disorders of autoimmune origin and cause significant physical and cognitive disabilities. The spectrum includes monophasic, multiphasic, and progressive disorders ranging from highly localized forms to multifocal or diffuse variants. [8] Monophasic events may be classified as clinically isolated syndrome (CIS), characterized by monofocal or polyfocal deficits without encephalopathy or acute disseminated encephalomyelitis (ADEM), characterized by polyfocal deficits and encephalopathy. [9] Recurrent disorders include multiple sclerosis (MS), neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorders (NMOSD) and serum antibodies to myelin oligodendrocyte glycoprotein (MOG)- associated demyelination. [10] International pediatric multiple sclerosis study group (IPMSSG) has proposed the criteria for

pediatric multiple sclerosis and immune-mediated central nervous system demyelinating disorders for diagnosis and research purpose. [11]

Of these, 33 (66%) cases were of acquired demyelinating encephalomyelitis (ADEM), 10 (20%) of transverse myelitis (TM), 5 (10%) of neuromyelitis optica (NMO), 1 (2%) of optic neuritis (ON) and 1 (2%) of multiple sclerosis (MS). The mean age of presentation was 7.7 years (range: 2-12 years). ADEM was the most common acquired demyelinating disorder in our study with mean age of presentation being 7 years which was similar to 5.5 and 6.14 years seen in other similar pediatric studies done by Torisu H, Singhi PD et al. [12,13] Although some studies have reported equal sex distribution. [14] Most common presentation in ADEM patients was encephalopathy with multifocal motor deficit and meningism similar to other studies. [12-14]

Of 50 cases, 24 (48%) were male and 26 (52%) females. History of preceding illness was present as upper respiratory infection /acute febrile illness and mean duration between preceding events and onset of symptoms was 7.24±2.9 days. All patients

diagnosed with ADEM had encephalopathy. Areas involved in descending order of frequency were subcortical white matter, basal ganglia, thalamus, brainstem, cerebellum and spinal cord involvement. MRI is highly sensitive in detecting white matter abnormalities and investigation of choice for demyelinating disorders. ADEM present with multiple hyperintense bilateral, asymmetric patchy and poorly marginated lesions on T2 weighted and FLAIR images on MRI. ADEM lesions typically involve the subcortical and central white matter and cortical gray white matter junction. Most of patients in our study present with subcortical white matter and brainstem involvement with occasional spinal cord involvement. Deep grey matter lesions involving basal ganglia and thalamus 54% which is similar to studies showing 49% to 60%. [12,15] Most of the patients responded well to the pulse dose of steroids on 3 month follow up.

Conclusion

Children presenting with new, subacute focal neurological deficits with history of some preceding event and in absence of trauma, metabolic derangements, or structural abnormalities should be suspected of having acquired CNS demyelination. These patients should be investigated with CSF analysis, serum antibodies and neuroimaging. ADEM is the most common among ADS. Early diagnosis and management with steroid therapy improves outcome in most of the patients.

References

1. Hintzen RQ, Dale RC, Neuteboom RF, Mar S, Banwell B. Pediatric acquired CNS demyelinating syndromes: Features associated with multiple sclerosis. *Neurology*. 2016 Aug 30;87(9 Suppl 2):S67-73.
2. Yeh EA, Graves JS, Benson LA, Wassmer E, Waldman A. Pediatric optic neuritis. *Neurology*. 2016 Aug 30;87(9 Suppl 2):S53-8.
3. Wilejto M, Shroff M, Buncic JR, Kennedy J, Goia C, Banwell B. The clinical features, MRI findings, and outcome of optic neuritis in children. *Neurology*. 2006 Jul 25;67(2):258-62.
4. Lucchinetti CF, Kiers L, O'Duffy A, Gomez MR, Cross S, Leavitt JA, O'Brien P, Rodriguez M. Risk factors for developing multiple sclerosis after childhood optic neuritis. *Neurology*. 1997 Nov;49(5):1413-8.
5. Waldman AT, Stull LB, Galetta SL, Balcer LJ, Liu GT. Pediatric optic neuritis and risk of multiple sclerosis: meta-analysis of observational studies. *J AAPOS*. 2011 Oct;15(5): 441-6.
6. Morales DS, Siatkowski RM, Howard CW, Warman R. Optic neuritis in children. *J Pediatr Ophthalmol Strabismus*. 2000 Sep-Oct;37(5): 254-9.
7. Deiva K, Absoud M, Hemingway C, et al. Acute idiopathic transverse myelitis in children: early predictors of relapse and disability. *Neurology* 2015;84(4):341-349.
8. Cañellas AR, Gols AR, Izquierdo JR, Subirana MT, Gairin XM. Idiopathic inflammatory-demyelinating diseases of the central nervous system. *Neuroradiology*. 2007;49(5):393-409.
9. Petzold A. Isolated, relapsing and progressive demyelinating diseases of the central nervous system. *J Neurol*. 2008;255(6):69-76.
10. Bar-Or A, Hintzen RQ, Dale RC, Rostasy K, Brück W, Chitnis T. Immunopathophysiology of pediatric CNS inflammatory demyelinating diseases. *Neurology*. 2016;87(9): S12-9.
11. Krupp LB, Tardieu M, Amato MP, Banwell B, Chitnis T, Dale RC et al. International Pediatric Multiple Sclerosis Study Group. International pediatric multiple sclerosis study group criteria for pediatric multiple sclerosis and immune-mediated central nervous system demyelinating disorders: Revisions to the 2007 definitions. *Mult Scler*. 2013;19:1261-7.
12. Torisu H, Kira R, Ishizaki Y, Sanefuji M, Yamaguchi Y, Yasumoto S et al. Clinical study of childhood acute disseminated encephalomyelitis, multiple sclerosis, and acute transverse myelitis in Fukuoka Prefecture, Japan. *Brain Dev*. 2010;32(6):454-62.
13. Singhi PD, Ray M, Singhi S, Khandelwal NK. Acute disseminated encephalomyelitis in North Indian children: Clinical profile and follow-up. *J Child Neurol*. 2006;21(10):851-7.
14. Gowda V, Shetty D, Madivala B, Benakappa N, Benakappa A. Clinical and radiological profiles, treatment, and outcome of pediatric acquired demyelinating disorders of the central nervous system. *J Pediatr Neurosci*. 2019;14(2):76-81.
15. Richer LP, Sinclair DB, Bhargava R. Neuroimaging features of acute disseminated encephalomyelitis in childhood. *Pediatr Neurol*. 2005;32(1):30-6.